

Investigating the use of Polarization maintaining FBG sensors for GW based SHM

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ABSTRACT

Guided waves (GWs) are very popular for the damage detection of thin-walled structures. They propagate large distances and relatively few may be used for damage localization. The problem with their use for complex structures is the signal processing. Due to the presence of multiple modes, and mode conversion and reflections from the structure boundaries and discontinuities the signal processing is indeed challenging. In order to reduce the complexity, lower frequencies are used to limit the excitation only to the fundamental modes. Even then the signal processing may be challenging. So efforts are focussed on the ability of some sensors to detect only a particular wave. This paper aims at investigating the suitability of the polarization maintaining FBG (PM-FBG) for this purpose.

Keywords: plate, guided waves, fibre optic sensors, spectral element method

1. INTRODUCTION

It is essential to inspect critical infrastructure for degradation or damage periodically. A range of different techniques have been used for this condition assessment. The monitoring of the condition of the structure in-service is termed as Structural Health Monitoring (SHM). SHM has the potential to reduce the maintenance cost and time significantly. Ultrasonic guided waves (GW) based inspection techniques are efficient SHM techniques as they can be used to monitor small cracks and damages over large structures using few sensors. However, the requirement of additional wiring and associated weight restricts the use of transducers in development of robust SHM systems.

In this regard, Fibre Bragg grating (FBG) sensors are a promising alternative for sensing due to their small size, less weight, and ability to be multiplexed and embedded inside the structure. Additionally, the optical sensors based on FBGs are immune to electromagnetic interferences. Traditionally, FBG sensors have been commonly employed for temperature and quasi-static strain measurements. More recently, they have been used for measuring acoustic signals.¹ The traditional approach of using FBG sensors in wavelength division multiplexing is not suitable for GW measurements due to its low sensitivity. A more recent approach is to use the edge filtering approach as shown in Fig. 1. The steep slope of the FBG improves the signal to noise ratio and increases the sensitivity.

The use of FBG sensors in the edge filtering configuration has renewed interest of the use of these sensors for GW. Recent research has focussed on the special abilities of the FBG sensors. Wu et al. used the FBG sensors in remote configuration to measure GW at 1000°. Wee et al employed the FBG sensors in self referencing configuration for reference free damage detection.³ Soman et al., used the FBG sensors and the difference in the coupling of antisymmetric and symmetric modes to perform mode filtering.³ They then used the mode filtering to improve the damage localization.⁴ Excellent literature reviews of the use of FBG sensors for GW measurements may be found.^{2,5}

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Figure 1: Edge filtering approach for increased sensitivity based on²

So the field of use of FBG sensors is quite nascent, due to the passive nature of the FBG sensors and the directional sensitivity, the methodologies applied for the traditional piezo based sensors and actuators cannot be applied directly to FBG based systems. Furthermore, some of the challenges faced by piezo based systems for the signal processing and damage mapping are still applicable to the FBG sensors. One of the key challenges is the mode separation and mode filtering. Typically for the damage detection the frequency of excitation is restricted to the domain where only the fundamental symmetric (S0) and antisymmetric (A0) modes exist. This makes the signal processing easier. Even then, for complex geometries with several structural features and complex shapes due to the boundary reflections and the mode conversion the signal processing becomes challenging even with two modes. Hence efforts are made to restrict the other modes or selectively sense only one mode. One possible way is to restrict the modes excited in the structure through the use specially designed actuators,⁶ special arrangements of actuators,^{7,8} or co-axially located actuators.⁹ The special actuators are costly and hence are not ideal for scaling to a large structure. Also, the special arrangement of the actuators limits the usable range of the network, as the actuator arrangement is optimized for one particular frequency.

Another solution is to identify the sensed mode through the use of special sensor arrangements. For instance placing sensors at two sides of the sample, may allow identifying the S and A modes. But this will need twice as many channels for interrogation which increases the cost significantly. The authors have recently presented an innovative strategy for mode separation using just one single FBG sensor.^{2,10} This concept is based on the different mechanism of the transduction of the wave with the fiber. But this approach is only useful where the relative ratios of the wavelength of the GW and the length of the FBG are in different regimes.¹¹ Also in order to realize the mode filtering the time required for measurements is considerably longer, making it challenging to be used in real applications. The authors also used birefringent fibres for selective mode sensitivity.¹² The birefringence was introduced by transverse loading of the FBG sensor and indeed selective mode sensitivity was seen. But due to the additional load on the structure, the end conditions were affected and the wave propagation in the loaded and unloaded sample were not comparable. Another way of achieving this birefringence is through the use of polarization maintaining FBG (PM-FBG). A recent study by Rao and Duan¹³ have shown that a polarization maintaining FBG sensor has selective sensitivity to S0 and A0 mode and has a potential to be used for mode separation. They report the sensitivity of the fast and the slow axis in the axial direction and perpendicular direction. But in the eyes of the authors they have not discussed the amplitudes of the excitation

in detail, and the experimental apparatus used does not completely use the PM-capabilities. Hence, this paper aims at furthering the understanding of the use of PM-FBG for mode filtering based on the selective sensitivity.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Schematic of the experimental setup is shown in Fig. 2. An interrogation scheme was used based on edge filtering, then output from a tunable laser was coupled onto a PM-FBG via an optical circulator. Two piezoelectric transducers (PZTs) with different sizes (PZT2 =10mm and PZT4=30mm) are located in different angle at the same distance (25cm) from the sensor. The signals were amplified via an amplifier (20x) and then supplied to PZTs (NCE51-CTS Corporation). A frequency of 50, 100, 150, 200 kHz was studied. The reflected light was directed to the third port of the circulator went through the polarizing beam splitter and then detected by a photo-detector and spectrum Analyzer. The time-dependent output of the detector was recorded by a computer-driven data acquisition system (Fig. 3). Efforts were made to align the fast axis to be perpendicular to the plate and the slow axis parallel to the plate. This will ensure that the coupling will not affect the mutual axes.

Figure 2: Experimental Setup

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the setup, the polarizer was used to obtain comparable magnitude of light in the two polarization direction. The signal was recorded using a optical spectrum analyzer and is presented in Fig. 3. The tunable laser was then centered on linear portion of the slopes P1, P2, P3 and P4. The responses obtained are shown in Fig. 4. The amplitudes are different owing to the different power of the reflected light and the slope at the different locations where the laser is tuned. But the signals appear well synchronised.

The normalized Hilbert envelope for the mean signal of P1 and P2 and P3 and P4 measurements are shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6.

The key differences can be seen at time $50\mu\text{s}$ where the amplitude of S0 wave are 150 kHz, 200 kHz and 250 kHz is appreciably more for the points P3 and P4 than at the points P1 and P2. Similarly, in Fig. 6 the A0 wave

Figure 3: Reflection spectrum of PM-FBG

Figure 4: Time domain data for 100 kHz excitation for 4 locations P1, P2, P3, P4

at 50 kHz and 100 kHz is more than that in case of P3 and P4. It should be noted that the plot is normalized so, relative amplitudes are compared. This is done to overcome the effect of the difference in sensitivity at the 4 points. These observations show, that the first peak is more sensitive to A0 wave than the second peak or in other words, it is not sensitive to the S0 wave. In order to validate that this performance is not because of the excitation characteristics of the PZT, excitation was repeated with a bigger PZT. The results for the two peaks are shown in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8.

Similar observations can also be drawn for the Fig. 7 and Fig. 8, that the first peak has higher sensitivity to the A0 wave, and lower sensitivity to the S0 wave.

4. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This research undertaken investigated if the two peaks of a PM-FBG have differential sensitivity to the antisymmetric and symmetric GW modes propagating in an aluminium plate. The initial results do indicate that there is a difference in the sensitivity of the peaks in the PM-FBG. This may be utilized if not for mode separation,

Figure 5: Surface plot showing the A0 and S0 modes at different frequencies for first peak for PZT4

Figure 6: Surface plot showing the A0 and S0 modes at different frequencies for second peak for PZT4

but for identification of the mode measured at the FBG. This may simplify the signal processing and improve the damage localization. The use of this differential sensitivity for damage localization is indeed the next step

Figure 7: Surface plot showing the A0 and S0 modes at different frequencies for first peak for PZT2

Figure 8: Surface plot showing the A0 and S0 modes at different frequencies for second peak for PZT2

for research.

The future work will try to study the directional nature of the PM-FBG. Also the response of the PM-FBG will be studied numerically and applied for mode enhancement. This technique may also be used for reference-free damage detection.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The research was supported by the project titled: Guided waves based reference-free structural health monitoring using fiber Bragg grating sensors (2020/39/D/ST8/00188) granted by National Science Center, Poland. The University of Warsaw team will like to acknowledge the funding support by the First TEAM programme of the Foundation of Polish Science (Project Number POIR.04.04.00-00-5E00/18), co-financed by the European Union under the European Regional Development Fund. The authors are also grateful to TASK-CI for allowing the use of their computational resources.

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